

European networks observing the atmospheric boundary layer: Overview, access and impacts

Chapter: Impact of current and future networks

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1 Introduction

Recent, significant advances in measurement technology and algorithm developments have made products from ground-based remote sensing profile observations increasingly interesting for stakeholders. Provided standardised operations, careful processing and adequate quality control (according to guidelines formulated by WG 3 and WG 4 of PROBE), these profiling products contain unprecedented spatial (horizontal and vertical) and temporal detail of variables characterising the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL). Sensor networks and retrievals are typically optimised for specific, individual applications, however as shown by WG2 of PROBE, synergistic procedures combining complementary sensors help to maximise exploitation of these rich data for a number of different purposes. While network observations from ground-based profilers are being recognised as valuable data sources by different communities, the measurements are still far from being exploited at their full potential.

Here, we highlight first applications of ground-based remote sensing ABL observations in emerging network structures. Our selection of applications is by no means providing a full picture of all impacts that ABL observations may have but rather showcases a number of representative examples. While some are established applications that are already integrated in operational procedures, others are still more experimental or even present a prospect for future developments.

The showcases will be of interest to a wide range of stakeholders, including academic research in many fields as well as national meteorological and hydrological services, environmental agencies, space agencies, renewable energy suppliers, urban planners and the safety and transportation sector among others.

2 Wind energy applications

Modern wind turbine rotors span elevations from 30 to 250 m above the surface. Depending on the atmospheric stability conditions, this corresponds either to a relatively shallow region of the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) in convective conditions, or the entire ABL (and above) under strongly stable conditions. Beside mean wind speeds and directions, turbulence induced by the terrain heavily impacts loads and power performance. In [Gandoin et al. \(2024\)](#), a number of application projects are described, all aiming at increasing the value of ABL measurements for wind energy purposes.

3 Solar energy applications

One of the challenges addressed by PROBE is to demonstrate the relevance of ABL profiling for improving forecasts of various factors relevant to solar energy application. The solar energy sector within the EU emerges as a dynamic and fiercely competitive industry, characterised by a constant stream of innovative technologies.

[Toanca et al. \(2014\)](#) explore the intricate relationship between ABL profiling and solar energy applications, by delving into the specific effects of cloud cover, fog, and aerosols on solar energy generation. Through a comprehensive examination of relevant research findings, case studies, and practical considerations, this document seeks to provide valuable insights for researchers, engineers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders involved in the design, implementation, and operation of solar energy systems.

4 Transport and aviation application - Fog alerts

Fog, characterised by low visibility due to suspended water droplets, has significant socioeconomic impacts worldwide, rivalling those of storms. Fog may be responsible for severe disruption at

airports, causes road accidents, and affects various operations including rescue and military activities. In arid regions, fog serves as a vital water source. Traditional fog forecasting methods using numerical weather prediction models face challenges in accurately predicting fog onset, spread, depth, and liquid water content due to the complexity of surface-atmosphere interactions. High-resolution numerical models and large-eddy simulations offer more detailed insights but are computationally expensive. Ground-based observations and especially remote sensing measurements, complement model forecasts by providing real-time information on both fog formation and dissipation processes. These observations enhance fog forecasting accuracy, offering valuable insights into key variables driving fog life cycle.

[Ribaud et al. 2024](#) focus on fog alerts presenting an overview of the product capabilities (accuracy, uncertainty estimates, readiness for operation etc...). Existing processing chains are also reported and published references are listed so that the reader can get more details on specific aspects if necessary.

5 Urban environments

The ABL over urban areas depicts a crucial zone of interaction between the synoptic-scale weather and direct surface-driven impacts on the atmosphere. The added heat and surface roughness, as well as the release of pollutants and reduction in moisture sources mean the urban boundary layer (UBL) is characterised by specific climate and flow conditions.

With the majority of the global population living in urban areas, they are increasingly moving into the focus of climate change adaptation. For example, global initiatives like The Covenant of Mayors are seeking solutions to make cities more resilient through adaptation measures. To make an appropriate roadmap to implement this planning should be based on data collection, modelling and simulations. Decision-makers usually have a wide range of tools at their disposal to address these challenges and develop resilience, but a better understanding of the microclimate and the environment of the settlement, as well the circumstances and sequences of extreme weather events could be essential to make informed decisions and choose proper development paths. The development of Urban Heat Islands or the propagation of air pollutants requires targeted measures. An improved understanding of processes in the UBL is critical for the evaluation of high-resolution numerical weather prediction and air quality assessment in cities, but also to inform sustainable urban planning and efficient disaster risk management (e.g. heat risk mitigation and adaptation).

[Körmöndi et al. \(2024\)](#) highlight a few examples of novel ground-based remote sensing profile data and products that showcase the importance of detailed ABL information for near-surface atmospheric conditions in urban settings. To ensure such data can be exploited effectively by municipalities, urban planners, or operational agencies, e.g. responsible for the monitoring and forecasting of air quality or microclimates, the information may need to be provided in targeted formats. Discussions are ongoing between different actors to develop the required communication strategies and to ensure applied products are made available that can be transformed into applicable decision support tools.

6 Environmental agencies and air quality

Environmental agencies and air quality institutions cover a large spectrum of operational activities connected to environment, land, water and air. This includes monitoring of the state of the environment and implementation of regulations. Monitoring networks provide data on which decisions are made and on which our understanding of the complicated processes involved in the natural cycles of the biosphere is based. Environmental agencies often also provide meteorological services for public and private sector and air quality monitoring and forecasting.

Ground-based remote sensing networks are becoming an increasingly important segment of observations. They provide high temporal resolution vertical profiles of dynamic variables (wind, turbulence), thermodynamic variables (temperature, atmospheric water vapour, water content, etc.) and composition (aerosols). Thus, state-of-the-art profiler instruments as applied within PROBE can provide high quality data and higher level products for the operational work of environmental agencies or air quality institutions, like analysing, monitoring, forecasting and issuing warnings related to air quality or meteorology influenced societal sectors.

[Ravnik et al. \(2024\)](#) showcase different case studies and operational user stories highlighting the valuable impact of the ground based remote sensing data in different application domains of environmental and air quality institutions. Online visualisation tools are also mentioned for the reader to get an insight on the type of information that is available.

7 Numerical modelling

In [Löhnert et al. \(2024\)](#) we showcase the impact of ABL profiling - mainly, but not exclusively through ground-based remote sensing - for applications in Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP). Besides being proven to operate in a 24/7, unattended manner with suited QA and QC measures, national weather services need to be convinced of the actual benefit of ABL ground-based remote sensing in NWP. For this, we highlight some of the latest results in the areas of model evaluation and short-term forecasting with focus on the dynamic and thermodynamic structure of the ABL.

First, the value for **NWP model evaluation** is shown considering NWP model performance for thermally driven valley winds in complex terrain using a microwave radiometer and a Doppler lidar. Furthermore, the European ceilometer network is shown to provide important reference data for evaluating model forecasts of Saharan dust outbreaks. Second, we show the importance of ground-based remote sensing for **continuously deriving forecast indices**. In combination with satellite information, a hypothetical network of ground-based microwave radiometers could significantly improve spatial information on forecast indices potentially leading to improved warnings for convective storms. And finally, this chapter shows some of the latest impacts of ground-based remote sensing in **data assimilation for convection resolving NWP**. One-dimensional and three-dimensional Observations System Experiments (OSE) with Doppler lidars and microwave radiometers are discussed, as well as results from Observation System Simulations Experiments (OSSE), the later highlighting to different methodologies to quantify the impact of hypothetical ground-based remote sensing networks.

8 Satellite applications

Well-established programs for satellites are dedicated to improving ABL profiling measurements but these data need calibration/validation from the ground and here is where emerging networks supported through PROBE play a vital role. High-resolution validation of aerosol, cloud, and precipitation profiles is challenging, therefore best practice protocols have been proposed lately in the scientific community. Several campaigns have been planned and some of them have already been successfully carried out. [Neumuc et al. \(2024\)](#) give an overview of satellite calibration/validation campaigns, ESA-European Space Agency (www.esa.int), EUMETSAT (<https://www.eumetsat.int/about-eumetsat>)- and NASA (www.nasa.gov) projects and missions which rely on instrument procedures and ABL products developed in PROBE.

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